

The Experimental Core: How LADIM-USB builds Venezuelan Electroacoustic Music

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Abstract

In a predominantly acoustic national music scene, the *Laboratorio Digital de Música* (LADIM-USB¹) or Digital Music Laboratory at Universidad Simón Bolívar has emerged as a fundamental pillar since 2003. Throughout its 23-year trajectory (2003–2026), LADIM has led the curation and performance of technology-mediated repertoire at international festivals and established collaborative networks with institutions such as SEAMS and CCRMA. The laboratory fostered the creation of 75 electroacoustic works—encompassing acousmatic, mixed and multimedia pieces—representing a significant portion of Venezuela’s electroacoustic music history. The ongoing research analyzes LADIM as a case study within the broader national context, examining its evolution from its genesis to its historical milestones. Furthermore, it surveys part of the composed repertoire and the produced research, addresses its preservation through the creation of a digital archive, and proposes a curricular renewal focused on a specialization program oriented towards experimentation and international collaboration.

1. Introduction

Electronic music started in Venezuela 60 years ago. With the organization of the III “Festival Latinoamericano de Música” it was built, in Caracas, the “Fonology Studio” (1966), that that would record the event and could serve as an instrument for the invited composers —like Schaeffer, Davidovsky, Tal or Schidlowsky— to show their progress with experimental music (Astor 2008). The Studio went under several restructuring processes that carried the distinctive sign of lack of funding and weak maintenance protocols. Nonetheless, it did mobilize and model a concrete inclination toward sound synthesis in the country with relevant outcomes. The — Studio or Lab, and at the end— *Instituto* had three directors who represented three different electronic music schools: José Vicente Asuar (Chile) and the *Elektronische Musik*; in a new

¹ <https://www.ladim.labf.usb.ve/>

chapter of the Studio Antonio Estévez and Raúl Delgado Estévez (Venezuela) and the *musique concrète*, and finally, Eduardo Kusnir (Argentina) and the Di Tella Institute / Columbia-Princeton Electronic Music Center alongside the American Tape music tradition.

In a country with a marked tendency toward acoustic compositions the electronic vocation has emerged as an occupation not universally practiced by all composers. In this sense, electroacoustic music in Venezuela thrives on the hard work of small groups, supported by individuals and a few institutions, among them, the Digital Music Laboratory at Universidad Simón Bolívar (USB).

The *Laboratorio Digital de Música* (LADIM) or the Digital Music Laboratory is located at the heart of Universidad Simón Bolívar in Caracas, Venezuela, and has played a leading role in the curation and performance of electroacoustic and technology-mediated music at the most prestigious international contemporary music festivals held in Venezuela —Festival Latinoamericano de Música, 2004-2016; Atempo, 2006—, Argentina (2006) and Mexico (2006, 2013).

In addition to sharing stage with institutions such as the Swedish Electronic Music Society (SEAMS) and the Center for Computer Research in Music and Acoustics (CCRMA, Stanford), organizing independent concerts and events, training composers and musicians, and producing a research corpus within the Master of Music program at Universidad Simón Bolívar, throughout its 23-year history (2003-2026) LADIM has helped in shaping the contemporary musical landscape of the 21st-century Venezuelan music scene, enabling the creation of a repertoire of 75 electroacoustic works by composers associated with it, including acousmatic, mixed, video, and live electronic pieces. LADIM's electroacoustic practice covers more than a third of the entire history of electronic music in Venezuela (1966-2025), so it is important to consider and reflect on the laboratory's efforts and challenges envisioning the future of its continuity.

As it is explained by Paraskevaídis (2004), ‘One of the endemic ills and endogenous characteristics that frequently slips in the understanding and transmission of the history of cultures and the arts of the ‘multi-mestiza’ America is that of starting —almost always— from scratch’ (Paraskevaídis, 2004). In our case, this research seeks to break with that cycle by confronting a fragmented history in need of organization. By rescuing scattered archives, recovering information from now-defunct websites, to build a new one, and documenting an ongoing practice that is still developing, this work provides institutional formality to the LADIM trajectory. Meanwhile, the achievements from Mexico, Chile, Argentina or Brazil (Sigal 2006; Schumacher Rati 2005; Alberton and Mosca 2008; Sigal 2012; Almeida and Oliveira 2022) serve as models to replicate and to learn from. We are writing a testimony of continuity, demonstrating that LADIM does not begin in a vacuum, but is a moving object and a history of resiliency. Here, creativity has functioned as a mechanism of resistance, transforming current funding scarcities into a catalyst for pedagogical innovation and the preservation of our sound heritage

This communication is part of a larger project submitted to the Universidad Simón Bolívar’s Dean of Research. The project's main objective is to document the activities of the *Laboratorio Digital de Música* (LADIM) concerning music, technology, and electroacoustic repertoire. This communication is closely linked to a related paper we published on the same topic in *Organised Sound* (Gómez & Morales, 2026).

2. Works and influences

LADIM was a project devised and achieved by the combined efforts of professors ‘Emilio Mendoza, Diana Arismendi, Raúl Jiménez, Francisco Díaz, [and] Adina Izarra’ (Noya 2007:231) from the Master’s degree in music at USB. Raúl Jiménez was director of LADIM from 2003 to 2004, Izarra from 2004 to 2017, and Luis Ernesto Gómez from 2018. Only Izarra and Gómez have provided artistic leadership. Their distinct influence is clear in their catalogues, scheduled activities, and the repertoire of the associated composers at LADIM.

The inaugural work developed under the framework of LADIM was Adina Izarra's *De Visée*², resulting from a fruitful collaboration between Izarra and plucked instrument player Rubén Riera. This work holds significant importance as it pioneered the use of ancient instruments, such as theorbo, in the electroacoustic music of Venezuela, and served as a structure further exemplified by Izarra's later piece *Toda mi vida hos amé* (with added video)³. These experiences represented models used by the composers working at the time at LADIM like Julio D’Escriván's *Acuerdos por alhambre* (2006), Leonardo Leal's *Fantasia* (2008) for theorbo and electronics⁴, or Miguel Noya's *Cryptochrome* (2013) for archlute and electronics.

These examples, as many others —Rubén Riera's *RoundMidnite* (2009) for 4 live laptops⁵, José Betances' *Neumas* (2015) for harp and live electronics⁶, Eduardo Lecuna's *Visiones* (2004)⁷, and Arocha's *Viaje para un piano imaginario* (2009)⁸, etc.—, were performed under the architecture of Max/MSP with a very strong presence of interactivity and video. The last period (2018-) has centered around PureData and SuperCollider.

At the frontier of the COVID19 pandemic (2020) the presence of poetry has been fundamental as Gómez is also a poet himself. The first works to appear were *Respiraciones circulares* (2019)⁹ and *Collage con nubes rítmicas* (2020), closely followed by *De mulieribus claris* (2019)¹⁰ by Morales and *Siluetas noctámbulas* (2020)¹¹ by Urdaneta. All these pieces can be seen as first experiments to then face the mixed repertoire: as is the case with *Ritmomaquia* (2021) for marimba and electronics¹² by Morales, *Prestidigitaciones* (2023) for string quartet and electronics¹³ by Gómez, and *Soliloquio a voces transparentes* (2024)¹⁴ by Pichardo.

The main difference between the two leaderships seems to reside in the creative output of the composers associated with LADIM and the repertoire produced during their artistic orientation.

² *De Visee* by Izarra: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pA_2sC_6HTM

³ *Toda mi vida hos amé* by Izarra: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GpoJ7COFAPo>

⁴ *Fantasia* by Leal: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cta3ZpaldDg>

⁵ *RoundMidnite* by Riera <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=P08bE8P2Iss>

⁶ *Neumas* by Betances <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IQb-LrqIEH4>

⁷ *Visiones* by Lecuna <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DLdmWyd5NW>

⁸ *Viaje para piano imaginario* by Arocha: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xC6RgHdRziM>

⁹ *Respiraciones circulares* by Gómez <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=U0comvNzVn0>

¹⁰ *De mulieribus claris* by Morales <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3HBCRUnyiUs>

¹¹ *Siluetas noctámbulas* by Urdaneta <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wesI0HjKOKs>

¹² *Visiones* by Lecuna <https://youtu.be/DLdmWyd5NW8?si=ya3R3I3o3qaCBZKy>

¹³ *Prestidigitaciones* by Gómez https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=E1SmPIWJ_7Q

¹⁴ *Soliloquio a voces transparentes* by Pichardo <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yIGc6-CRmH0>

As for the activities, Izarra described a performance more inclined to inviting professors, masterclasses, and a sustained presence as curator at different national and international venues, strengthening international networks; on the other hand, Gómez has described a performance prone to hosting events as the seminar ‘Si hay una nostalgia es por el futuro’, organized with the help of Venezuelan composer Mirtru Escalona Mijares, or the formative activity at Centro de Arte Los Galpones with Venezuelan composer Miguel Noya as facilitator.

3. Research

Scholarship of electroacoustic music began in Venezuela when the electronic medium was allied with an academic institution. It seems natural that this very important aspect of a laboratory is achieved when the formative activities and part of the efforts of the institution are linked with a university (Babbitt 1960). It was the case with CEDIAM-UCV and the research conducted by Segnini (1994) on the history of electroacoustic music in Venezuela.

The academic production linked to the Digital Music Laboratory and the Master’s in Music program at Universidad Simón Bolívar¹⁵ reflects a technical and aesthetic evolution within the field. The whole spectrum of research can be summarized as follows: algorithmic music (Jiménez 2002); software development (Díaz Esposito 2004); assisted improvisation (Peraza 2013); history and repertoire (Noya 2007; Arocha Bernal 2009; Navarro Salerno 2010); and analysis (Álvarez Acero 2012).

A number of research outputs also address history and repertoire, such as the EMS proceeding by Arocha and Izarra (2009). In addition, collaborative creation is explored in book chapters by Izarra (2012) and Noya (2012), while bioacoustics was central to the collaborative efforts discussed in a round table by Izarra and Keller (2015).

The efforts of the composers associated with LADIM who conducted electroacoustic-related research after their time at the LADIM-USB must also be noted. This is the case with the doctoral dissertations of Rojas Ramírez (2015), which offers a multidisciplinary approach to cultural hybridity (*mestizaje*) and nationalism in Venezuelan electroacoustic music between 2000 and 2010; and Álvarez Acero (2022), a deeper development of the first investigation (2012), which delves into typomorphology approaches to acoustic and electroacoustic writing.

Moreover, the laboratory’s influence is reflected in the research produced by both current members and former affiliates now established in other academic posts. These independent trajectories encompass diverse scholarly outputs, including studies on improvisation (Izarra 2022), the interpretation of mixed works (Arocha 2023), the fragile state of electroacoustic music pedagogy in Venezuela (Pérez Valero, 2024) and analytical approaches to the music of Alfredo Del Mónaco (Álvarez 2024; Morales 2025a, 2025b). More recently, the history of LADIM itself has become a central research theme (Gómez and Morales 2026).

Beyond these contributions the current period includes venturing into other related fields like digital lutherie, live-coding and spatialization. While continuing with established branches such as algorithmic composition and software development, the lab will seek support from the university search groups in quantum physics, computer graphic, and 3D-printing, as well as strengthen collaborations with national institutions and international partners, with remote or

¹⁵ Measured with Master’s theses.

on-site laboratories, composers, and performers. These are some of the engagements to schedule in this new period.

3. The Notion of a Lab

We have delineating several core functions that define the concept of an electroacoustic music laboratory within an academic framework:

- Formation and pedagogy;
- Scientific performance, encompassing various forms of research;
- Creative practice, including music composition, performance, software development;
- Curatorship and production, referring to the ability to organize events centered on music, technology and electroacoustic repertoire; and
- Preservation and sustainability, ensuring the continuity of efforts through web dissemination, archival storage, documentation, and platform maintenance;

It can be argued that fulfilling these tasks is essential for the proper operation of such facilities, providing an objective framework to examine their institutional performance. A method remains to be proposed —based on existing literature— that systematically weights these listed functions based on the history of laboratories. Such a method could incorporate new categories to more accurately represent the complex obligations and requirements these organizations entail today.

In the case of LADIM, with 20 plus years of experience, there is a pressing need to manage its extensive archive of composition. Furthermore, as LADIM belongs as part of continuity of a long tradition of electroacoustic music in the country, a further responsibility arises: the documentation and preservation of the country's broader electronic music history —the next task in our list.

4. About the Certificate Diploma

In order to expand the formation capacities, the first task in our notion list, the foundation of a new program under the frame of LADIM seems natural. This objective is being set up harboring the desire to revitalize the entire structure: dynamize the Master's program, and serve as another platform offering specialization in this kind of repertoire in the country, nurturing, in the same way, the LADIM activities with new professors, students and the movement of development.

It would be a four quarter term program specially offered to composers and performers with an ideal final presentation in the form of a concert with both composers and performers interacting with each other, exposing a personal artistic project developed during the course of the final quarter.

During these four terms, and alongside the usual subjects of getting to know the code and the software, there will probably be one subject about the canonical repertoire, one about digital lutherie or electronic instrument building, and one about interactivity.

5. Final remarks

This is an ongoing project. We expect to gather the majority of the repertoire from LADIM to then jump to contribute in the building of the big archive of electronic music in Venezuela, for LADIM represents a very important portion of that same history.

As for the Certificate Diploma, this course will help the Laboratory in many different ways: drawing attention of new composers and performers, funding it in part to organize new big and little events around the city, and potentially, around the country in special venues. There will be a win-win relationship between the course, the Laboratory, and the country scene, as the emergence of new alternative spaces of experimentation is a potential possibility we would love to help on bringing, particularly in the other universities where music is a subject of study.

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